

“HYPERSTITION AND AUTHENTICITY.

PURIFYING THE PREFERABLE FUTURE THROUGH THE ETHICS OF IDENTITY”

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ABSTRACT

In a society where social acceleration crushes creative thinking in its rapid and heuristic component, the problem arises of how a strategic foresight can be the true identity projection. The risk of projecting automatic imaginative mechanisms linked to a false identity is high. Only an ontologically pure dimension can be powerfully dynamic and projective. We propose the harmonious application of some ethical coaching tools to be combined with foresight, to ontologically purify identity. Values, in fact, represent a precise identity expression. The success and veracity of any future projection depends on its purity. The precise determination of the goal profile is energetically linked to the real intention and the probabilistic possibility of realizing the prediction. By applying this concept before developing each prediction we can obtain a reclamation of intentionality that is preparatory and pre-exists the subsequent correct application of imaginative techniques.

Keywords: values, identity, hyperstition, foresight, coaching

COACHING AND THE FUTURE

The coaching profession is in constant contact with the Future. When Coaching entered companies, automatically developing strategies and action plans aimed at tomorrow was a natural step (Whitmore, 2017). Today Coaching offers many techniques and approaches to facilitate the individual or Team's ability to create their Preferable Future (Clutterbuck, 2020). In Coaching we unlock individual and organizational potential, exploding it into its best version of the Future. The simplest traditional method is that of the double chair, where we directly project the person to explore the effects of a possible prediction (Schreiber, Hellams, 2009). He can thus find out if what he had planned was really in line with expectations. Another very structured and effective way is

that of the Time-Line, which can even be considered as a very specialized technical branch of Coaching. It can practically resolve any critical situation in various ways (James & Woodsmall, 1988). When we want to expand our medium-long term forecast, we can use the Mandala. A very powerful visualization technique, which by affinity manages to bring out the evolutionary path in perspective, accompanying the person through 4 distinct phases: current situation, letting go, learning, achieving (Offeddu, 2023). The effects of predictive possibility are sometimes disconcerting. Another very technical way of doing an individual foresight exploration is level alignment. By projecting the person into a future role or condition, we ensure that we carry out what can be defined as an ecological check. How sustainable is the person's chosen future, for the person themselves? (Dilts, 2018).

From these elements, a certain familiarity of Professional Coaches can emerge regarding the theme of the Future, especially with regard to its co-creation, its impacts and its sustainability. If we want to find an important point of intersection between Futurology and Coaching, we can certainly refer to the fundamental principles of another technique: Appreciative Coaching (AC) (Orem, Binkert & Clancy, 2007). This innovative hybridization between Coaching, Constructivism and Appreciative Inquiry (AI) (Cooperrider & Whitney, 2007) was able to intuit and develop 5 principles of Future generation which are very close to the concepts of Hyperstition and Future-back. In fact, among the 5 principles of AC, in addition to the Constructionist, Poetic and Positive, there is the Simultaneous-Anticipatory binomial (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Appreciative Inquiry principles

These two principles are the key to the generation of scenarios, since in them lies a true anticipatory simultaneous maieutics. The question that generates an intuition, the “powerful question”, has an immediate effect on the person's ability to predict. The moment it is asked, a variable of possibilities opens up that did not exist before. The exploration of this variable, the

predictive choices made by the subject, generate an "anticipation" of the preferable Future, which retroactively influences the present itself, in its potential and possibilities. This retrograde effect actually produces a real Hyperstition (Holt, 2020). The generated Future influences the present, and even the reading of the past, with a domino effect. The climber's method had already proposed a reverse action plan in the past (Fasciano, 2021). However, only AC can unleash the predictive energy of a quasi-quantum foresight.

HYPERSTITION IN THE PREFERABLE FUTURE

Once we have clarified the fact that Hyperstition has a retrograde effect, we can relate it to the three horizons model (Sharpe, B., 2020). In fact, every prediction in H3, the third horizon corresponding to the imagined future and imbued with intention, influences H1, the present, and determines H2, the actions and events that connect the present with the imagined future. As we have said, it corresponds to the climber's model, where a retrograde path is defined that leads to the present. This in general. What happens in the case of specific cases, where the imagined future does not correspond to the trends? Here we can integrate the model taken as reference with the cone of Voros Futures (2022) (Fig.2). We insert in the ray of the Preferable Future the path determined by a Hyperstition generated by a single subject, or by an organization, which tends to deviate from the foresight Trend taken as reference.

Fig. 2 – Voros Future Cone and the three horizons

It is at this point that we ask our some questions on the merits. How can we make sure that the prediction of this specific Preferable Future is as correct as possible? Is it possible to imagine a different quantum power generated by a Hyperstition launched by a pure and determined intention, compared with a Hyperstition hybridized by different and dissonant intentions and influences? In other words, can an authentic desire for a Preferable Future be more true and impactful than an induced desire? How many times in achieving a task or objective have we felt empty in achieving it? How often do we commit ourselves to objectives that are not ours, but "in favor" of others? And how many times have our attempts failed, perhaps because in the end that type of challenge wasn't exactly what we really wanted?

In Coaching there is already a tool that carries out this check. It is called an ecological objective check (Global NLP, 2022). The Coach helps the client to check their goal, to understand whether it is worth undertaking an action plan or not. Beyond this, our observation wants to focus on the first moment of forecast generation. We want to determine exactly how the individual and collective subject constructs their intention in generating their own Preferable Future. How does the subject, in its complexity, construct its own vision of the Future? What tools does he use?

Research carried out in the field of social philosophy has amply demonstrated the crucial importance of the system of individual values (Patania, 2024). We are talking about what Erich Fromm defined as "Humanistic Ethics". According to the investigation into the psychology of morality carried out by this author (Fromm, 1947), and confirmed by many subsequent authors (Von Thun, 1998) (Dolan & Garcia, 2002) (Geldart, 2014) (Mattone & Vayda, 2016) (Barrett, 2024), the subject can decide about his own future in two ways: either by resorting to one's intelligence, or to one's reason. Since intelligence is mainly concerned with solving practical problems, in most cases it automatically comes into play. Its role is to logically determine the quantitative aspects of phenomena in a superficial way. For this reason it can be defined as two-dimensional: results and quantitative data. It is a logical-mathematical computational intelligence. When the value aspect comes into play, the person comes into play instead. The tool that is added as a third dimension is precisely ontological: it defines the essence of objects and processes and the ethical value that the subject, recovering his own identity, carefully evaluates. Wanting to use a mathematical expression:

2D Intelligence + 1D Sense of Purpose/Values = 3D Reason

So, exasperating this concept, we can try to say that while intelligence is flat, reason is three-dimensional (Patania, 2023). Each prediction of a defined preferable future will be of different quality depending on the type of instrument (Intelligence or Reason) that the subject will choose, more or less consciously, to use. By definition, the retrograde influence of Hyperstition is the more powerful the more authentic (Audasso, 2018). It follows that the natural space within which Hyperstition is powerfully unleashed is 3D: three-dimensional, guided by a pure subject identity, which will have consciously chosen to use its own Reason.

THE HEALTH COACHING MODEL AND AUTHENTICITY IN FORESIGHT

The literature supporting the importance of authenticity in determining pure intention and subsequent success is relevant (George, 2003) (Avolio & Gardner, 2005) (Susing, Green & Grant, 2011) (Al Gurg, 2023) (Spaulding & Barrett, 2024). The more authentic we are, the more effective we are. This evidence gives further support to the new model of the Health Coaching path presented by the Italian Association of Health Coaching (AIHC) (Fig. 3- Patania, 2023b). According to this model, which we can combine with that of the three horizons, the H1 phase is preceded by a purification of the person's Value system, to determine the true CORE. By activating the use of Reason, Values, Sense of Purpose and Identity come first, in a self-clarification operation. Your beliefs and mission are well defined. Only then do we move into the H1 moment of the here and now in asking questions aimed at generating the Preferable Future (H3).

Fig. 3 – The new Health Coaching session model with three horizons included

How is it possible to operate in this sense? How can we work in a scientific and evidence-based way in such a sophisticated world as that of values and identity? First of all, it is necessary to use the linguistic techniques offered by ontological-transformational coaching (Echeverria, 2013). This particular type of coaching, which can easily be hybridized with Appreciative Coaching, is specifically aimed at investigating the person's identity, the true "being". This helps a lot in the dialectic of the coach-client interview, when we want to speak to the Reason-driven part of the person and not just the Intelligence-driven part. Therefore, in a foresight technique on the definition of a pure Preferable Future, the AC technique, with its 5 Principles, should be integrated with the dialectics and principles of Ontological-transformational Coaching.

In addition to this, it becomes important to work on the actual ethical system of the subject, individual or organization, defining the reference value system. In this regard, several very powerful and validated Values Coaching tools can be used, where the Values Barrett Centre system is the one that provides the greatest amount of information in organizations and is now

validated (Barrett, 2017). They are models that can be hybridized and which for example can integrate a vision based on needs and personal fulfilment (Maslow, 1968), with a tri-axial system of social, emotional and economic components (Garti & Dolan, 2021). We can thus combine the health coaching model with the integration of value models on the cone of futures. As with the Health Coaching session, the purification of the subject's identity is inserted in a previous phase, working on values. (Fig.4)

Fig. 4 - Integrating the cone of futures with values (health) coaching models

Thanks to this determined and focused work, we simplify and reduce the subject's ethical system to the essentials, in order to extract maximum authenticity from it. This powerful authenticity will generate an equally powerful Preferable Future prediction in H3. Greater authenticity, greater purity and effectiveness of the retrograde Hyperstition that will be generated. In H2 it will be necessary to do a periodic predictive check on what is defined as Consistency in the subject's ethical system (Gambill & Carbonara, 2021). What is classically defined as “walk the talk” is achieved by putting your value system into action according to a pure intention. It is necessary to avoid any possible moral inconsistency in the system of values applied to real life (Dolan, 2016). Verifying the actual authenticity and coherence in the implementation path of the Preferable Future will guarantee a further retroactive check on one's identity and the consequent pure intention.

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of our argument is to unhinge the cage of presentism and open the future to the dimension of desirability. The social acceleration (Rosa, 2017) to which we are subjected makes us alienated in the present. We are strangers to ourselves, while being extremely productive in diligently fulfilling our tasks and duties. By not caring about the meaning of our actions, we lose the meaning of our lives and end up losing ourselves. This clearly affects our ability to predict and plan the future, which is almost obvious and flat. The same thing applies to both individuals and organizations. Identity is a function of responsibility. A company that knows who it is can more easily generate powerful and enlightened foresight. Only by recovering our identity and creativity can we truly challenge ourselves to become fully responsible for our perspectives. To do this we must be able to suspend our daily attention of Doing. Instead, dedicate ourselves to what Hartmut Rosa calls functional deceleration, that is, our profound reflection dedicated to Being. In full harmony with the ontological principles of humanistic transformation, in fact, *Agere sequitur Esse*: actions are a simple consequence of an authentic identity. Using the language of the Future expressed in classical language, one could say: *Iperstitio sequitur Esse (Identitas)*. The courage of authenticity can emerge from our identity, guided by our values. We have many tools to do this in a technical and appropriate way. Thanks to this emergence of authenticity, it is easy to expect that subsequent applications of strategic foresight techniques will be even more effective, penetrating and powerful. This is already documented by experiences found in the field of professional coaching, with examples such as Appreciative or Evolutionary Coaching. Today, Health Coaching also contributes methodologically to the co-design of optimal Humanistic Transformation, through the publication of its own skills model (Crescenzi et al. 2024).

Beyond what has been described, we propose a final systemic reflection. Due to the affinity of its mission to explore the future, the alliance of purpose between Coaching and Futurology can find many operational synergies. Both work to generate scenarios in a creative and evolutionary way. The experiential part provided by the former can contribute both technically and effectively to improve the very powerful foresight modeling of the latter. For example, mixed groups can be envisaged where coaches and futurologists exchange experiences and techniques, to increase their ability to impact the system. A dualism that can make the proposal to support companies and the civil world even more convincing. We therefore hope that our presentation on Hyperstition and Authenticity, in addition to contributing to the research, experimentation and application of foresight models, can open up spaces for collaboration between Futurology and Coaching.

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